

Notes

Studies on 12-Heteropoly Niobotellurate

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ONLY a few heteropoly compounds of niobium have been reported^{1,2} in the literature. The present short communication deals with the preparation, characterisation and X-ray crystal diffraction studies of a new heteropoly compound containing tellurium as the hetero atom.

Water solutions of telluric acid and freshly prepared³ potassium hexaniobate, $K_7HNb_6O_{19} \cdot 13H_2O$, were taken in the molar ratio of 1:12, refluxed for two hours and then after leaving the solution in atmosphere for two days, it was finally crystallised under vacuum when small white needle shaped crystals came out which were recrystallised thrice from hot water. The analysis of the compound was done by chemical and flame-photometric methods. The percentage of potassium, niobium and tellurium in the compound was found to be 11.87, 41.90, 4.75 against the theoretically calculated values 11.78, 42.09, 4.82 respectively. The percentage of water and oxygen, calculated by difference, came to 41.48. The individual estimations of hydrogen content in the compound came to 2.01 and hence the percentage of water was 18.20. From these percentage composition data, the compound has finally been represented as $K_8H_2[TeNb_{12}O_{88}] \cdot 27H_2O$ according to the views suggested by Lindqvist⁴.

X-ray crystallographic data and molecular weight determinations :

The unit cell dimensions were determined by using rotation and Weissenberg X-ray diffraction photograph for a single crystal of the compound. The crystal data were as follows :

$a=14.62$, $b=28.56$, $c=10.68 \text{ \AA}$ ^o
 $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90$, hence the system is orthorhombic.

The volume V per unit cell was calculated to be 4459.404 \AA^3 . The space group was uniquely established as $D^2_2h-P_{nnn}$ from the following systematic presence of reflections : hkl ; no condition, okl ; $k+l=2n$, hol ; $l+h=2n$, hko ; $h+k=2n$; hoo ; $(h=2n)$, oko ; $(k=2n)$, $00l$; $(l=2n)$ and hkl ; $h+k+l=2n$. The last condition gives the number of molecules per unit cell Z to be 2. The observed density, measured by floatation method, ρ_{obs} , was

found to be 1.96 gml^{-1} . From the relation $\rho_{obs} = \frac{1.66.M.Z}{V}$, the molecular weight 'M' of the compound came to 2632.6, against the theoretical value 2648.53, which definitely concludes that the compound is monomeric.

References :

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Migration of Nonconductors (Iodine and Derivatives) during Electrolysis

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Though normally a non-conductor is supposed not to migrate while a current passes through a solution of the same, we have observed some nonconductors, particularly iodine and some of its compounds to have the remarkable property of electrical migration. The present preliminary note describes the salient features of such migration.

Experimental

The simplest way to observe such migration is to electrolyse an iodine solution in alcohol between two platinum electrodes in any U-tube (height 15 to 30 cm, diam. 20 to 35 mm) but a better way is as follows. To start with, the U-tube is filled up as shown in Fig 1A with the help of a pipette, and a D-C voltage of about 200 to 500 volts is applied between the electrodes. A current of a few hundred microamperes would pass through the solution. Methyl and ethyl alcohols (anhydrous and aqueous), glycols as also pyridine are the most convenient solvents to be used for such purpose.

Taking a typical case say iodine in absolute alcohol (its molar conductivity is more or less equal to that of a weak electrolyte such as acetic acid in